

**LES CONTRAINTES DU PROCESSUS DE LA TRADUCTION
DU LANGAGE DIPLOMATIQUE ET POLITIQUE :
IMPLICATIONS DANS LA TRANSPOSITION DIDACTIQUE /
THE CONSTRAINTS OF THE TRANSLATION PROCESS
OF DIPLOMATIC AND POLITICAL LANGUAGE:
IMPLICATIONS FOR DIDACTIC TRANSPOSITION**

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This article explores the unique challenges encountered when translating diplomatic and political language, highlighting its implications for didactic transposition, meaning the application of these translations within an educational context. An analysis emphasizes the specificities of diplomatic and political language, which is characterized by often complex vocabulary, figurative expressions, subtle nuances, and specific cultural connotations, requiring a particular translation approach. Lastly, an aspect underlining the importance of a nuanced and well-informed approach to translating diplomatic and political language is discussed. Translators must be aware of cultural implications and diplomatic subtleties while maintaining the integrity of the messages when transposing these texts into the educational and pedagogical framework. Teaching translation in these fields must take these challenges into account and help learners develop the specific skills necessary to succeed in this highly specialized area.